
Factors Influencing Knowledge Sharing Culture among Postgraduates

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Abstract Knowledge sharing is important aspects in organization or education in ensuring knowledge can be transfer to one another. Culture seems to give an impact on this practice. However, due to limited studies in Malaysia, this research is carried out to study the factors influencing knowledge sharing culture in an educational institution. This research emphasis the factors of communication, motivation and trust., This research adopted quantitative survey as methodology gathering data and the data was using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). All the hypothesises tested were accepted. Communication and motivation is the main factors students sharing information while trust is really need to have before students share. The findings suggested that the addition of communication skills, rewards and motivation with trusted build would elevate the students' sharing skills as well as the influence in it has on the overall performance of Information Management students.

Keywords Knowledge sharing, Factors Knowledge sharing, Culture knowledge Sharing, Motivation, Communication, Trust in knowledge sharing, Education

1. Introduction

This chapter discuss matter pertaining to the general context of study. The purpose of this chapter is to provide an overview of the research which includes problem statements, research questions, objectives, scope as well as significant of the study and a chapter summary. Knowledge and success of students should be simultaneously improved as time passes by. Knowledge, being an important driver of success, should be continuously disseminated throughout an organization. According to Singhsabdu (2011), effective management of knowledge is important for organizations to remain competitive in today's market. Knowledge Sharing involves knowledge transfer and development of competencies via sharing and learning culture (Yang, 2007). Knowledge sharing among public and private establishment has continuously been the subject of research throughout the body of literature due to the positive impact it offers to organizations engaging in the initiative. In the context of university students, Rafaeli & Ravid (2003) acknowledged the ability of students to gain positive, creative and cognitive learning outcomes when making Knowledge Sharing an everyday culture. The same notion was also shared by the Faculty of Information Management at Puncak Perdana Campus whereby it hold strongly on the importance of Knowledge Sharing being a learning culture among their students of different background and level of study towards producing an all-rounded successful graduates. Acknowledging the importance of Knowledge Sharing for the betterment of success rate among students, this study therefore aims at investigating the learning culture factors that influences Knowledge Sharing practices among post-graduate students with

particular focus made on the Faculty of Information Management at Puncak Perdana Campus, Selangor. The findings is expected to provide an overview on the learning cultures that affects Knowledge Sharing adoption among students which may benefit not only the faculty within the scope of this study but also other higher education institutions in Malaysia towards integrating the Knowledge Sharing culture among their students which is hoped to result in better quality graduates.

2. Literature

According to Flemming Poulfelt (2000), sometimes, ambiguous signals are provided by top management when they make statements such when 'Information Sharing is vital' while, at the same time, they do not alter any of the mechanisms that help to lift barriers. Perhaps it would be better to balance between saying and doing, while at the same time setting more frontal in capital. At the current state, knowledge hoarding has been dominating practice among students which has been a major stopping block towards diffusion of the Knowledge Sharing culture. Exchange or dissemination of explicit and tacit knowledge, experiences, ideas, skills and information from person to person or within group of students is called Knowledge Sharing and with performing these, students get to interact between one another either via physical or non-physical means. In contrast, Knowledge hoarding involves the act of being secretive and unwillingness to share things that they know with others which an this could be due to unwillingness to sacrifice their time to share with others, avoiding unfair free-riding, remaining competitive, and so on.

Beyond that, the lack of Knowledge Sharing culture among students could also be tracked back on the lack of motivational inputs that could drive behaviors. Factors such as the lack of recognition (i.e Dean's List award), lack of scholarship offerings, poor communication skills, lack of time, being inactive on social networks, diversity in culture, distrust, low motivation, being unaware of its benefit, lack of interaction, fear of not receiving recognition, and so on has also been linked to the lack of Knowledge Sharing adoption (Singhsandhu, 2011). As a result, not only does it sacrifice on performances but it also disables enjoyment of the full value of Knowledge Sharing by higher education institutions (Chinwei, 2012).

Therefore, with regard to the hesitance to adopt Knowledge Management among students despite the proven benefits, there is a need for further investigation into the reasons behind it. As such, it is vital to scrutinize the reasoning of their reluctance to share knowledge towards placing efforts to overcome them. With this in mind, this study thus aims to inspect the influencing factors with particular focus made on aspects of communication, motivation and trust.

Objectives

The aim of this study would lead to the following objectives:

- A. To examine the communication as the factor influence knowledge sharing culture in UiTM Puncak Perdana.
- B. To determine the motivation as factor affecting knowledge sharing culture.
- C. To determine Trust as factor influence knowledge sharing culture among postgraduates students.

The study of knowledge sharing culture in Malaysia is still lacking and this can help become one of the contributions to Malaysia Education specially and generally to others. Besides, this research is hoped to contribute towards extending previous research done in similar areas. This study extends in culture of knowledge sharing. The instruments used and develop may be duplicated and replicated from previous research but in different setting focusing on culture. Through this study, it will help in gaining understanding about

factors influence the culture of knowledge sharing and being committed towards building the culture. The findings from this study will allow the Faculty of Information Management decision-makers to be informed about the knowledge sharing practices among student. If the results indicate substantial program effectiveness, then further resources should be dedicated to improve the knowledge management syllabus and further contribute to the identification of other knowledge sharing barriers. It is hoped that it would enhance and better encourage students, academicians and public to involve in information and knowledge sharing practices.

Knowledge Management

Knowledge management is a structured and coordinated technique that includes knowledge processes such as development, usage, storage, exchange, transfer and retrieval of knowledge to improve business efficiency and use of knowledge that includes information and human knowledge (Arntzen et al., 2009; Adhikari, 2010; Gu, 2004). This allows knowledge not only to be handled but to flow at the right moment for the right people to be implemented and to generate value in terms of sales, revenue, time or cost savings for the company more maybe. Knowledge management (KM) has also been described as "the structured and systematic process of generating information to build value that can be used to improve the teaching-learning environment" (Adhikari, 2010; Gu, 2004). The most important reason for this evolution of KM is when there is a concept about the importance of knowledge in our life and also as organizational resources.

For decades, the definition of KM existed, but often, organizations adopted it as a theory only and did not apply it as practice. KM is not only limited to corporate but also has importance in the education field. This is because institutes have the tendency to replace old knowledge with new ones, in particular the ones needed to prepare the instructions. KM is only enhanced when organizations facilitate creation, acquisition, transformation, storage, provides & receive feedback as well as the dissemination of stored knowledge in order to develop new insights (Bhusry & Ranjan, 2012; Khamzah et al, 2017).

Knowledge can be classified into tacit and explicit ones within the context of KM. According to Jamaluddin (2005), tacit knowledge is a type of inside-human knowledge such as experience and know-how that is context-sensitive, flexible, experienced, learned or know-how-based, and often subjective or intuitive, casual or informal, highly personal, and simply not easy to formalize. It is not easy to pass on implicit information to others for all of those justifications. There are also explicit knowledge in the form of documents, manuals, procedures and technique, databases, books, case as well as reports in either print or electronic formats and those are formal and systematic. This can make it easy to connect, and communicate. Consequently, knowledge managers often need to distinguish implicit from explicit knowledge, since they have their own property. This information can be easily controlled and used, through understanding it. Knowledge management is about the organization's knowledge management process, who knows what and who is working on what (Jamaluddin et.al., 2005).

Knowledge Sharing

Knowledge seems to be a very broad term and its boundaries and definitions are openly described. Sharing information refers to the transmission or exchange of knowledge, ideas, experiences, or even skills from one person to another. This involves either face-to-face or non-physical means of communication to connect with others. Conversely, information hoarding is the intentional withholding of information that would help and benefit others (Behnke, 2006). The exchange of knowledge often applies to processes in which individuals make their own information available to others, internally stored and/or externally sourced. In real life, online environment can be either direct or indirect. Knowledge sharing can achieve its degree in online settings by

uploading sources, providing links to sources that are already available online or by writing a post or response directly such as those from Wikipedia, Q&A forum, videos tutorials on YouTube, blogs and the like (Asterhan, 2017)

With reference to Willem and Baleens (2007), they describe the sharing of information as a practical understanding which enables organizations to conduct various operations. The sharing of knowledge also means that one unit is more affected by others experience in the process of knowledge exchange and processing than by the acquisition and transmission of knowledge from one unit to another (Argote et al., 2000). The primary aim of knowledge sharing within an organization is to provide the right people with the best information.

Flemming Poulfelt (2000) expressed in their article that developing a database for knowledge-sharing enables organization to bring with it a variety of other issues, motivating workers to participate and use them, update data and maintain consistency. He also noted that accessibility is only one of several components in a culture of information sharing. Practice of knowledge sharing is a mechanism that goes beyond knowledge transmission; it also involves knowledge interpretation and the use of knowledge within the unit itself. Thus, the exchange of experiences and know-how between departments is just one aspect of the sharing of information as it does not result in the practical application of common knowledge. Ugochi ishika et al. (2013) on the other hand described sharing of knowledge as being the conduct of a person who disseminates his or her knowledge and information to other colleagues within an organization and as a mechanism of contact between two or more individuals involved in the procurement and knowledge acquisition". Likewise, knowledge exchange can be defined as a voluntary and social process which are able to transfer, absorb and reuse existing information. It works in a highly dynamic setting and thus, requires prompt response to survive in a rapidly changing setting. Information in these institutions are divided into two forms namely academic information such as teaching, seminars, publication and recording as well as organizational or operational services and support functions. In addition, top management should also keep up with the emerging information and make it more available and access university students.

Determinant of knowledge sharing

The organizational challenge of today is to develop and encourage a culture of knowledge exchange within organization, as well as to avoid the thought and actions of industrial age groups (Husin et al., 2017). Husin et al. (2017) also discussed on the perception of understanding information sharing culture whereby the feeling of being threatened caused people to become rather defensive. There are also factors relating to rewards, paranoia and distrust for knowledge credit. Others fear that if they focus on sharing that they lose concentration on their primary jobs while some perceive it as a waste of time or rather an irritating thing to do. Further to that, Husin et al. (2017) found that top seniors are in the opinion that difficulties in developing incentives, creativity and publishing the concepts in company objectives are among the hindrance to Information Sharing.

Ugochi Ishika et al (2013) did a study on factors influencing Knowledge Sharing among postgraduate students at University Malaya with the primary goal to identify disparities between their knowledge on KS and behaviours commonly found in corporate organizations. Questionnaire surveys were used as means for first-hand perspective of the contributing factors for the sharing of knowledge among postgraduate students. The research found that the driving factors for sharing of knowledge among postgraduate students differ from what existed in the corporate world, mainly due to difference in their goals and objectives.

Yuen and Majid (2007) on the other hand studied on issues attributed to the lack of sharing of knowledge among students and contrasted the two types of task, goals and context of the organization. Charband (2018) in his study concluded that sharing of knowledge enhances the effectiveness and quality of the services provided.

Previous Related Research

Figure 2.1: Framework (Adapted from: Al kurdi et al., 2018)

Al-Kurdi et al. (2018), they explored the factors affecting knowledge sharing culture with the trends and future opportunities as they involved multiple factors that related to larger culture. The determinant of KS was classified into four areas namely individual, organizational, technological and cultural with some sub-points to explain the knowledge sharing culture in Higher Education Institution.

Figure 2.2: Framework (Adapted from: Al Alawi, 2007)

Based on study conducted by Al-Alawi, (2007), they looked into the factors that strongly affect the success of knowledge sharing. They found that all factors (refer figure 2.2) had a positive relationship with KS in an organization.

Figure 2.3: Framework (Adapted from: Charband, 2018)

Charband (2018) on the other hand explored the factors influencing knowledge sharing among educational organization with some open issues regarding their behavior and mechanism. Results indicated that there is significant impact of each factors on educational organization.

Knowledge Sharing Culture Factors

Culture refers of belief that is expressed by the behavior of a society or organization (Asrar Ul Haq, 2016). According to Al Kurdi (2018), culture can be considered as organizational or institution culture or national culture or knowledgege culture itself. Sharing culture can be explained as a situation that "A society that has gained distinctive levels of expertise in exchanging, and using information and knowledge that positively influences the organization in achieving its goals and goals."The definition may be most appropriate because it points out all aspects of knowledge management practice, the skills required and understands to create a community, and the intended outcome(Al Kurdi, 2018).

Based on Al Alawi (2007) reviews, organizational culture have uniqueness in their identity which can be visible and invisible at same time which reflected through values, mission of organization, actions and perception of insider of an organization. At the same time, a research review by Fullwood (2018) stated that organizational culture is the most significant factor to effective knowledge management which can be both enabler and barrier. Culture characteristic as studied by Fullwood (2018) are collaborative, sociable, open, flexible and conducive surrounding for sharing. Fullwood also discuss how culture influences people to share and are found to be caused by the individual characteristic and physical structure of an organization instead of leadership and competition. Fullwood further mentioned that in culture will result in different level. Organizational culture in academician or institutional played major part in building sharing practice which need collaboration, less pressure, motivation and clear support to encourage it to be success. According to Soley and Pandya (2003), culture has much definition such as an group of people who share perception and values system. Culture is collective of attributes which always evolve and dynamic. Ugochi ishika (2013) had investigate the factors affecting knowledge sharing among undergraduate students in a public university in Malaysia and came out with a theory that the influencing factors are of personal attributes such as trust and self-efficacy as well as technological factors like availability and usefulness of technology. Culture of an organization or higher education can be the key explanation for a success or failure in the practice of knowledge management and implementation of information sharing. Culture is also characterized as an expectation community, unwritten rules, and shared history that affects behaviour and belief in social and thought. Both contributors and managers should address unfriendly culture of information.

There will be reaction to the concept in both positive and negative environment. There would be some resistance from users in culture, lack of interest, and not even willing to explore. When participation is excluded, the worst will come because people feel that sharing information will affect their work and have not been embraced by managers and executives.

Culture is a term that incorporates an institution's and its individual values, behaviors, and behaviors. Organizations are individual groups and each organization has a specific culture which describes how people relate to each other (Goffee & Jones, 1996). Culture is a very important aspect because it can greatly influence human actions and as a result, reforming and improving is nearly impossible. Based on study by Gupta & Govindarajan (2000), the effect has been extended in intangible ways, such as the query styles and comments, formal and informal expectations, reward program orientation and people's involvement are some specific modes of knowledge exchange behavior that may have shaped the organization's culture. The organizational culture also includes six major categories, according to Gupta and Govindarajan (2000), information systems, individuals, process, leadership, incentive system and organizational structure.

3. Methodology

Research Paradigm

Research paradigm is an essential element in helping to design every research or study. It serves as a way of thinking about and how to do things (philosophy) (Saunders et al., 2016) which offers a basic structure that will direct the researcher on the basis of assumptions in understanding the existence and reality of any topic of knowledge. Research paradigm also defined as wider framework that comprises perception, understanding and belief of theories and several practices in conducting research step by step. Research paradigm assists in proper selection of research methodology as well as determining most appropriate data collection and data analysis approach.

Research paradigm could be categorized into two types namely positivism and interprets; in which this study focuses on the positivism approach since this study is empirical nature. By determining the causal relationship of the outcome, this study will be testing the relationship between variables that have been selected. This study will use deductive approach as the researcher use survey method and a positivist. This is based upon past literature whereby the variables selected for the theoretical frameworks will be tested to reach onto a hypothesis to determine validity of the variables studied. The researcher is using mono method as the data collection only uses a single method namely the questionnaire while corresponding analysis procedures (graphs and statistics) will be presented in form of numerical data.

With regard to the purpose, strategy, planning and approaches of this research paradigm, quantitative data collection allows for measurement of results and constructing numbers to achieve a valid finding at the end. Quantitative methods are also best used in determining validity of hypothesis or theory. A larger sample will assist in providing better generalization of a theory based on a larger set of population which would not be quite possible via qualitative approaches.

Generally, research design is the overall plan of action that will be taken in carry out any research activity or project. Sekaran and Bougie (2016) stated that designing the plan for gathering and analyzing data is required after identifying the variables and formulating the frameworks. It aims at getting the most convincing and reliable solution in answering research questions. Quantitative research gathers numerical data by clarifying perceptions scientifically. Among approaches in quantity research includes the use of descriptive analysis, correlation, experimental and competition of causal effect. Population is a group of people that may have same traits , attributes, and characteristic which would have huge impact on the research. Population identification also enables the research to explain the boundaries and state conditions that limit where, when, how, who included or excluded in a study. (Tuckman,1978). For this study, the selected population is the postgraduate student of the Faculty Information Management at UiTM Puncak Perdana Campus.

The target population in this research is postgraduate students in UiTM Puncak Perdana Campus, focusing only Faculty Information Management. According to University statistics, they are a total of 225 postgraduate's students in Faculty Information Management as per July 2020.

4. Data Analysis

Analysis involves the process of synthesizing data that were obtained from data collection stage. For this purpose, four essential steps are to be followed namely data cleaning, non- bias responses, reliability test and validity test as well as descriptive analysis. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 25.0) was used as means of conducting all data analysis and synthesis processes.

A reliability test is conduct using Cronbach Alpha reliability test that will determine how far each items related with others and how the consistency. The higher the Cronbach's Alpha value, the higher the reliability (0.6 or more).

Table 4.1: Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient Rules

Cronbach's Alpha	Internal Consistency
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$	Good
$0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$	Acceptable
$0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.6$	Questionable
$0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.5$	Poor
$0.5 > \alpha$	Unacceptable

Next step is doing the factor analysis between variables using factor data reduction function in SPSS for factor analysis such as Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test as the assumption test. The adequacy result sample measured by KMO should be more than 0.60, while, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity need to achieve lower than 0.05 for the result. Frequency analysis is the analysis the allowing the result views from frequency table, bar charts, histogram or pie charts and others mapping chart. Descriptive analysis is analyzing result of questionnaire that was distributed online using the statistical software SPSS version 25.0. All the data collected were measured in term of their average values of variables, their mean scores, standard deviation, minimum value and maximum values as well as the dispersion of variables (Variance, Standard Deviation, or range). In view of that, this study uses tables and figures to present the result of research variables. The methodology and research design for the factors influence knowledge sharing culture in UiTM Puncak Perdana among postgraduates students. It explains precisely on how the data will be collected and analyzed to meet the objectives of research. This research was conducted using quantitative survey based on the positivism paradigm stated and was pilot tested before distributed to targeted respondent. To analyze the data, SPSS version 25.0 was used using tests of reliability, validity, descriptive, inferential and frequency analysis which will explain later in chapter 4. First, the reliability test is conducted using one of the SPSS function. In the reliability test, Cronbach's Alpha value will determine the validity of research variables. In accordance with Leech et al. (2008), there are several measures of reliability such as reliability for one score or measure, internal consistency reliability for multiple item scales, reliability for nominal variable, assumptions for measure of reliability and conditions for measure of reliability. This study used internal consistency reliability for multiple item scales (usually for Likert Scale) which is the most commonly use is Cronbach's Alpha. The value is based on the average correlation of items that was previously identified in factor analysis. The Cronbach's Alpha values are accepted if greater than 0.7 is used for further study. The Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient Size Rule of Thumbs is used, and the result of Cronbach's Alpha value being reliable is provided in table 4.1.

Table 4.2: Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient Rule

Cronbach's Alpha	Internal Consistency
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$0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.6$	Questionable
$0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.5$	Poor
$0.5 > \alpha$	Unacceptable

The variables in this research were Trust, Communication and Motivation. After conduct the reliability test, all study variables were found to be accurate, valid, reliable and appropriate for further analysis, as shown. Communication at $\alpha = 0.817$ is the variables with the highest Cronbach Alpha Value, while Trust variables display the lowest Cronbach Alpha Value at $\alpha = 0.576$. However, all variables are seemed to be acceptable and valid for further analysis. The reliability test indicated that these factors achieved $\alpha = 0.910$, the acceptable Cronbach's Alpha Values. There is no unreliable research variables evaluated in this research. This therefore confirms the instrument used for this study as being highly reliable.

Table 4.3: Research Variables

Factor	Variable	No of Items	Cronbach's Alpha Value
1	Communication	9	0.817
2	Motivation	14	0.796
3	Trust	10	0.576
Dependent Variable	Culture	15	0.634
Overall	All factors	37	0.828

From table, we can see the reliability analysis for the Communication variable is .817 thus indicating its reliability for use in this study. The same applies for both Motivation and Trust whereby their Cronbach's Alpha values were considered acceptable and reliable for further study. There were also questions in the questionnaire that used to know the culture of knowledge sharing In Puncak Perdana generally, and the value of the reliability is 0.634 and make all together reliability values with all factors is 0.828 show clearly valid and reliable for analysis. Next is the step to provide the considerable amount of evidence that gathered to method variance influences, field measures and the relationship between these measures. It is important to recognize the bias produced in the findings. As explained by Anaqi (2019), result for common method bias should achieve less than, 50%. This is supported by Podsakoff and Organ (1986) in Masrek (2015) whom also stated that if result validity for common method variance achieves more than 50%, it is considered as threats and problems. The results of this study showed that the data collected were free from threats or problems by common method variance because the single factor described in this study is less than 50%. Table 4.3 presents the cumulative bias with total variance explained.

Table 4.4: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	1.433	35.834	35.834	1.433	35.834	35.834
2	1.023	25.575	61.409	1.023	25.575	61.409
3	0.945	23.637	85.046			
4	0.598	14.954	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Factor Analysis

There are two factors analysis which are exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis. This section will discuss the finding of the factor analysis using factor data reduction function in SPSS for factor analysis such as Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin KMO and Bartlett's test as the assumption test. According to Masrek (2015), the adequacy result sample measured by KMO should be more than 0.60, while, Barlett's Test of Spehericity need to achieve lower than 0.05 for the result. However according to Leech, Barrett, & Morgan (2008), the KMO adequacy result should more than 0.70 and the Barlett's Test need to achieve lower than 0.05 for the significant result. The reduction technique is to statistically identify a reduced number of factors from a greater number that named measured variables. The established variables are then called Latent Variables, since they are not explicitly measured or calculated. This study contains many variables which make it complicated. Therefore, inter

correlated variables are brought together under more general, underlying variables. In this study, KMO result in measuring the sample adequacy is 0.714 achieved more than 0.70 value as stated by the Leech's and members. The Barlett's Test of Sphericity result is .000 proved that the variables in this study are correlated highly enough. This also bring means the data is reasonable and suitable for factor analysis. Then, below is the table 4.5, the communalities of this study. Every item's communalities of the study got result above than 0.5. Frequency analysis is the analysis that allows the result to be viewed from frequency table, bar charts, histogram or pie charts and others mapping chart. In this section, there were several tests done based on given percentage. In the questionnaire, four (4) questions covered namely gender, student's age, Course Programme and Mode of study, all of which were analyzed using the frequency table. The respondent's demographic profile serves as intent for analyzing the study of relevant data. Table 4.6 indicates the frequency and percentage of the study's demographic profile.

Table 4.5: Descriptive Statistic for Demographic Variables

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Gender	150	1.00	2.00	1.6067	0.49013
Age	150	1.00	4.00	2.7267	0.85056
Programme	150	1.00	5.00	2.7333	1.42681
Mode	150	1.00	3.00	1.4267	0.73591
Valid N (listwise)	150				

Table 4.6: Total Value of the demographic profile for gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	59	39.3	39.3	39.3
Female	91	60.7	60.7	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

The table indicates the total value of demographic gender in this survey which is dominated by females. The male frequency is 39.3% compared to 60.7 % females.

Figure 4.1: Gender Percentage

Descriptive Analysis

This section discussed the descriptive statistic of the result from the questionnaire distributed online. The knowledge sharing culture factors was measured using the statistical software SPSS version 25.0. All the data

collected were measured in term of their average values of variables, the mean, standard deviation, minimum value and maximum value of each indicator for each research variables and measure the dispersion of variables (Variance, Standard Deviation, or range). According to Nassaji (2015), the aim of descriptive analysis in research is to describing an event and its attribute or characteristic. Nassaji also stated that a qualitative research can also be analyzed quantitatively after examines the data qualitatively to related with relevant ideas or themes for comparison or evaluation phase. In such, finding data can be analyzed quantitatively using frequencies, averages, percentages or others to relate each other. The results of a study can be clearly presented using pictures, table, graphs or any data presentation method. In view of that, this study will using table and pie chart graph to present the result of research variables.

The variables were measured using 5 point Likert Scale where 1 is strongly disagree and 5 is strongly agree. The descriptive analysis will include all the variables involved from the dependent variables and independent variables. This section will present the independent variable first which Communication (Comm), followed by Motivation (Moti), Trust (Tru) and Knowledge Sharing Culture itself.

The descriptive of independent variables are the factors that influence the dependent variable. The table 4.12 is the overall Mean score of independent variables which are Communication, Motivation and Trust. Above indicates the list of the average mean score in the descriptive analysis of the independent variables measure in this study. It indicates that among other independent variables the Trust has the highest mean with a score of 3.973. Whereas the second highest is motivation at 3.81 while the least is communication at 3.440. The main objective is to expose the data analysis of this study from the 150 respondents. This chapter segregates the results into some section which are sample profile, model analysis, demographic analysis, frequency analysis, descriptive analysis, inferential analysis and others test to check the reliability and validity. All the results is collected by online questionnaire. Common method bias performed was. Next, it is also studies and discusses the descriptive analysis of the research result. It is aiming to answer the research question 1(RQ1), research question 2 (RQ2), and research question 3(RQ3), which are all about the factors influence knowledge sharing culture in UiTM Puncak Perdana Campus. These are summarizing of the finding:

- i. Reliability analysis: Shows that in this study used all valid factors or variables after the factor analysis is carried out and are relevant for further analysis.
- ii. Assessing common method bias: The findings showed the single factor of total variance is only 35.85 percent less than the benchmark value of 50 percent which means that the data obtained is free from the question of common method variance.
- iii. Factor analysis: The result shows that no new independent variable is detected, and all variables are clean loads.
- iv. Descriptive analysis for variable items showed that all the study variables had the average mean score indicating the respondents were tempted to agree with the measuring variable.
- v. Analyzing regression showed that all of the parameters are relevant and significant.

5. Conclusion

In this study, knowledge sharing culture has been identified to have a positive relationship with communication. In answering the first research question stated, test of survey result proved that communication is the clear factors as the variable has a sample mean of M 0.221, Standard deviation of STDEV 0.675 and P values of 0.000. The results of the Pearson's Correlation study showed that there is a positive relationship between communication and culture of knowledge sharing at 0.420. Through this work the hypothesis of relationship

between communication and the culture of knowledge sharing is accepted. These findings have been supported by the previous study by Asrar Ul Haq (2016) who mentioned that communication as not just act as promoter to knowledge sharing but also as an enabler that increases transferring of knowledge from one another. Effective communication is one of the influencing factors in knowledge sharing culture. Most respondents said they do not share knowledge due of poor communication and interpersonal skills. This finding is similar to Yaghi et al. (2011) which found that a lack in communication skills affects the knowledge sharing practice and culture. However, they are some other issues that affect communication such as difficulty in convincing members on the values or benefit a knowledge they want to share. Other than that, it was found that people most likely prefer to share among themselves and their group of members rather than publicly with others. It was due to fear to seek new knowledge and it could be a mismatch in opinion which could offend others. It was also found out that the lack of knowledge sharing culture among students are due to fear for undue credits. They are afraid that the knowledge are shared to others without due credit to them, owner or founder of the knowledge. Interestingly, according to the study, we can see that there are many students resisting sharing of information because there is a lack of communication and interaction between those seeking knowledge and those with knowledge. The information is kept with them or only shared only to those who are willing to share with them. From the survey we could also see that language is not the main barriers as it received the highest disagreement vote from respondents.

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